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APPLICATION OF REINFORCEMENT LEARNING METHODOLOGIES IN SOCIETY OF MIND COGNITIVE ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract

Learning is simply not an algorithm that defines rules on how agent can learn, but various other parameters than of an algorithm which has its impact on agent's learning behavior. There are various Reinforcement learning methodologies and types but the Question is how natural can these learning algorithms be on agents? This research paper investigation is concerned with understanding animal and human learning and the importance of agent's various internal and external parameters that have the effect for human-like learning ability. We focus on infantry agent that ameliorates with time and gets intelligent.

Keywords- Reinforcement Learning, Human Learning, Society of Mind Approach to Cognitive Architecture (SMCA), Fungus world testbed.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper reports on A Society of Mind Approach to Cognition and Metacognition in a Cognitive Architecture within which learning abilities are being investigated. The work colligated with this paper includes building an agent's knowledge from

null to actually recognize, understand and exhibit in his future events.

This paper provides a framework for implementing Learning mechanism to an agent whose environment is complex and varying. It not only provides a platform to implement learning capability but also suggests and demonstrates the importance of considering varies other factors that have an effect in learning. It can be internal and/or external. Internal factors like- emotional state, metabolic activity, at what instance it encounters with new things, its short and long term memory, external factors like- rewards from environment, information from supervisors (in case of supervised learning) and likewise.

Learning is a process of knowing the unknown. As humans, we have the ability to act on our environment and observe its effects [4]. We learn by constantly interacting with our environment and Reinforcement Learning is one such process that does the same. Today's RL agents are successful in interacting well with the environment and learns which is greatly relied upon rewards from the environment. But human learning is unlike the above.

Learning begins with the necessity, establishing driving idea and learns until a saturation state is reached or until its needs are fulfilled [5].

This raises implementation issues in adopting human like learning abilities in agents. This paper provides a solution where-in-which available Reinforcement learning algorithms can be enhanced to make agents learn as humans learn.

II. LEARNING IN SMCA

In SMCA, there are fifteen agents ranging from reflexive agents to metacognition agents [1]. An agent is that which senses and acts in its environment. Metacognition agent can observe its own progress in performing cognitive tasks or metacognitive regulations. Also it's been said that reflective processes with learning capabilities can lead to metacognition mechanisms. Agents with metacognitive mechanism are needed for optimal decision-making capabilities where environment is dynamic and complex.

An agent can be made to learn and impose the learned knowledge thereafter. I will be discussing Learning mechanism and how other factors plays important role. Consider an example of a reactive agent. A reactive agent in SMCA has perceptual way and holds decision making and behaviors for intended action [1]. Reactive agent performs goal oriented behaviors. If agent selected is Reactive-fungus, its goal oriented behavior is only to collect fungus. Now, question arises how can a agent type like Reactive-fungus know the presence of other resources, recognize its importance, and how and when can this agent exhibit the learned knowledge to collect them in future[1].

In SMCA there are sophisticated agents like metacontrol and metacognition agent which shows higher performance rates. But, in this paper, it is an attempt to bring up a simple agent like Reactive agent to learn, behave effectively and demonstrate progress by increasing various performance measures.

Fig. 1 Basic Architecture for implementing Learning Algorithm to correspond animal learning.

Eventually portraying how important various factors are- emotional state, microeconomic activities, metabolism rate and likewise.

Fig. 1 shows an architecture for implementing learning algorithms which resembles animal learning.

The Learning process starts with null knowledge of resources that it is unaware of. Once agent start its goal oriented task, the learning process is exhibited as below:

1. An Agent perceives from its perceptual range and move towards nearest resource. Each time an agent comes across a resource it asks environment for its reward. If the agent encounters any resource other than its goal based behavior on its way, it queries environment for the type. Environment will respond with the type and reward. A reward can be any value or reinforcement [3]. As a value in SMCA, agent makes its use for calculations in artificial microeconomics [2]. This reward may or may not be known to the agent. For example, Reactive-fungus coming across gold for first time, as gold is unknown it tries to find its importance. As

environment rewards gold as equivalent to 5 ores and makes it to understand that gold increases agent performance as number of goal collected increases [2]. Agent learns from this reward by updating its knowledge base, setting priority and importance for each resource that it encounters.

2. After collecting resources agent continues towards its goal oriented behavior. There might be possibility of agent coming across a learned resource type on its way towards goal oriented behavior. In such a case, depending upon agent's interest, priority and condition/state of agent, it makes a choice whether to collect or not. Once done with either of choices it again continues towards its goal oriented task.
3. The agent continues this process until its survival or number of cycles limited.

III. Q LEARNING USAGE

Learning is a sign of intelligence when made to act that pays off. Q-learning is a technique under reinforcement learning that works by ascertaining

$$Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow \underbrace{Q(s_t, a_t)}_{\text{old value}} + \underbrace{\alpha_t(s_t, a_t)}_{\text{learning rate}} \times \left[\underbrace{r_t}_{\text{reward}} + \underbrace{\gamma}_{\text{Discount factor}} \times \underbrace{\max_a Q(s_{t+1}, a)}_{\text{max future value}} - \underbrace{Q(s_t, a_t)}_{\text{Old value}} \right]$$

Fig. 2 Q Learning Algorithm

2. **Discount factor (γ):** This determines the importance of future rewards as a factor of 0 makes agent opportunistic where as 1 will make agent strive for very high rewards.

What values are to be assigned takes lot of careful investigations, understanding nature of learning habits of human beings such that agents exhibit human like learning abilities. One of the most challenging aspects of Artificial Intelligence is to make machines behave like humans. Thus when agents are supposed to express human like learning habits, inferring the nature of human learning is essential.

The parameters of Q Learning can be selected and assigned in different ways. Both these values can either be of type:

1. **Constant and Consistent:** Learning rate and Discount factor can be chosen to be constant. It means throughout the life time of agent values for both these factors will remain same and persist same (consistent) for all types of rewards from the environment.

an action-value function. It is one such learning mechanism that gives the expected service of taking a particular action for a particular state, thereafter following a fixed policy [9]. Learning needs to follow optimality assumptions where an agent has to learn optimal policies, even though it may not follow them always. Q Learning algorithms can separate exploration from control. The Q Learning algorithm is shown in Fig. 2:

Q: S X A → R

Q - the matrix holding Q value.

S – State; A – Action; R – Reward.

Learning depends on two parameters:-

1. **Learning Rate (α):** This determines to what extent the newly acquired information will override the old information. A factor of 1 will completely override the old information and factor of 0 will make agent not to learn from new information.

2. **Constant and dissimilar:** Learning rate and Discount factor can be chosen to be constant. It means throughout the life time of agent values for both these factors will remain same, but will be different for different rewards from the environment.

3. **Varying and Consistent:** Learning rate and Discount factor can vary depending on the agent's internal state. It means throughout the life time of agent values for both these factors can vary, but will remain same (consistent) for all rewards from the environment.

4. **Varying and dissimilar:** Learning rate and Discount factor can vary depending on the agent's internal state. It means throughout the life time of agent values for both these factors can change, but will be differ for different rewards from the environment.

Among these last case is efficient and varyingly dependent which makes learning; building knowledge base and demonstrating varied learning experience perfect for agent whose environment is complex and have various kinds of rewards. This holds good for

demonstrating human like learning experiences. Humans hold many types of emotions and we act with emotions rather than with logics. Thus considering the internal states of human/agent is essential.

IV. HOW MUCH VALUE IS TO BE GIVEN FOR LEARNING RATE AND DISCOUNT FACTOR?

This section explains what values are to be given for resource types. This depends on many factors and is domain specific. For illustration, let's consider Reactive-ore agent. This agent only knows about ore, it's worth and reward value from environment. Collection of ore becomes agent's goal-oriented behavior. Now, as in fungus world test-bed other resources includes small fungus, big fungus, bad fungus, crystal, gold, medicine [1]. Below I have specified for these resources what values can be given. This is specific to need and objectives of one such specification. These values have to be chosen carefully and versed such that it reflects true, desired display of learning from the agent.

For ore agent:

- Fungus:
 - Higher learning rate: As fungus is essential for agent's survival, it is always good to keep learning rate high. This makes agent to learn quickly the importance of fungus.
 - Highly rewarding – Discount factor can be kept as low as 0.2. Whereas 0 makes agent to divert its attention from collecting ore to fungus, which shouldn't happen.
- Ore:
 - No learning required: because collecting ore is agents goal oriented task. But can be made to learn to acquaint it in dynamic environments.
 - Highest reward: because collecting ore is its goal oriented task. So when acquired it must be of highest reward.
- Gold:
 - Learning with high rate: single gold is equivalent to 5 ores, making agent to learn with high rate builds agent's knowledge to give more priority such that even gold can be collected to satisfy its goal.
 - Much rewarding

Fig. 3 Steps involved in implementing Learning process

- Bad fungus:
 - Learning should be high: But this should be treated as negative. Bad fungus increases metabolism rate which is undesired, so agent learns that eating bad fungus is of bad choice. Thus next time when it encounters such bad fungus it ignores. Thus coding will be such that it dismisses consumption which for other resources it is to consume.
 - No rewards: this must be an obvious value. There is no reward granted for bad fungus.
- Medicine:
 - Learning depends on condition of agent. But it certainly learns if it consumes when not in need as well. When agent has metabolism rate medium/high, it will search for medicine to bring its metabolism rate down; this happens if agent is aware and uses its intelligence to make a decision to search for medicine. Else, agent has to undergo a learning process. This happens only if on its way to collect ore encounters a medicine then it comes to know that during medium/high metabolism rate consumption of medicine will reduce the rate so that it survives longer.

Moreover, it can be such that during medium/high metabolism rate agent searches for suspicious items in search for medicine (considering agent doesn't have prior knowledge of environment). But this constitutes another learning process; again agent can be made to learn in these situations as well. Thus we can also have multiple learning processes for different application on a single agent.

- Not much rewarding: As it is in interest of agent that it determines its importance.

Thus, to demonstrate, agent has to understand that medicine will be source of cure when it eats bad fungus, such that it immediately tries to find nearest medicine to lower its metabolism rate [1].

Likewise agent learns with environment and depends upon those two parameters.

V. IMPLEMENTING LEARNING IN FUNGUS WORLD TESTBED

The Learning encompasses four stages as shown in fig. 3. The steps are as follows:

1. **Encounter:** Learning process begins at the very start of agent's life, but how knowledgeable it

gets depends on how agent looks at suspicious things, when and at what instance it encounters with resources, decisions taken based on its available knowledge, emotional level and likewise.

2. **Identify:** Once it encounters, it has to identify. Agent succeeds in identifying then learning process takes place which is described in next step. On failure, it queries environment to get the type, then store the type for later use (if again agent comes across this resource, it can use this as prior knowledge). By this, agent could experience some affect from consumption of resources then agent has to learn from this experience.

Learn: Agent performs Q Learning with extended care by check decision making parameters, generating Learning rate and discount factors values by considering agent's internal states. i.e. emotional level- desire, intention, metabolism rate. Also get the reward value from environment. Calculate Q value using Learning rate and discount factors generated which also depends upon resource that it encountered. Thus Q Learning Algorithm is applied and corresponding values for Resource types are updated.

Graph 1 Performance of SMCA lower levels to higher level agents

3. **Act:** Moving forward towards goal oriented behavior. Making predictions on which direction to choose by considering finite state machine.

VI. SIMULATED RESULTS

Simulated result shows that Learner demonstrates the potential to learn as when it encounters with the resources in its environment. Furthermore, observation of the activity of Learner shows a kind of personal selection that it makes in exhibiting an action. It also shows significant learning when its energy level is high, and with higher rewards. It does by increasing its learning rate. Being in bad emotional state, higher metabolic rate or lower energy level, agent ceases to learn as it lacks interest and decreases its learning rate parameter, so that its intention is driven to find remedial measures or carry out its goal oriented task.

Experiments are conducted on agents in SMCA using Fungus world testbed [1]. Agents from different levels of Architecture were employed for this experiment. In this experiment to show the effect of learning on an agent, we considered comparisons between reflexive agent, reactive agent, the reactive agent with inclusion of learning mechanism- learner and BDI agent.

The agents are experimented with same percentage (100%) life expectancy and resources (refer graph 1).

VII. CONCLUSION

This research paper illustrates how to implement learning with various parameters like metabolism rate, emotional state, previous knowledge, energy level and likewise. Making use of available SMCA model and fungus world testbed, simulated results showed that learning algorithms which make use of these parameters demonstrated resembles of animal-like learning behaviors. This also showed the enhancement of Reinforcement learning which showed that an infant can be brought about to be knowledgeable and further act intelligently. This research gives a new roadmap for connecting animal learning onto agents in virtual world.

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